

UNIVERSITAT DE
BARCELONA

MONITORING REPORT 2024

Implementation of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA) at the University of Barcelona

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Monitoring report 2024

Reported at the Governing Council meeting of 5 March 2025

Office of the Vice-Rector for Quality Policy
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**IMPLEMENTATION OF THE AGREEMENT ON REFORMING RESEARCH ASSESSMENT (CoARA)
AT THE UNIVERSITY OF BARCELONA**

MONITORING REPORT 2024

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1. University of Barcelona CoARA Action Plan 2024–27

Context

In 2022, the European Commission launched an [initiative](#) to create a network of organizations committed to reforming the research assessment system.

As a result of this initiative, the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) was published in July 2022, with the aim of maximizing the quality and impact of research assessment practices.

Following the publication of the agreement, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)) was established in December 2022. The University of Barcelona has been a member of the coalition since its inception and has actively participated in several CoARA initiatives.

It is in this context that the University of Barcelona undertakes to advance the reform of research assessment and seeks to work constructively to help establish the framework for a new research assessment culture. As a leading institution in high-quality teaching and research, the University of Barcelona embraces the four core commitments of the Agreement. Accordingly, the UB is committed to:

- recognizing the diversity of contributions and career paths in research, in accordance with the needs and nature of the research;
- basing research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation, in which expert peer review is central, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators;
- abandoning inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics; and
- avoiding the use of rankings of research organizations in research assessment.

In January 2023, the UB CoARA Working Group was established, comprising the vice-rectors responsible for research, doctoral studies, and teaching and research staff, as well as the delegates for open science and the internal promotion of research, supported by a research management officer. The UB CoARA Working Group led the development of a [first version of the UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27](#), with the aim of implementing the supporting commitments of the Agreement in addition to the four core commitments. These include three commitments to enable the move towards new research assessment criteria, tools and processes, and three commitments to facilitate mutual learning, communicate progress and ensure that new approaches are evidence informed. The Action Plan was presented to the Governing Council of the University of Barcelona on 8 May 2024.

In July 2024, the Vice-Rector for Quality Policy and a second research management officer joined the UB CoARA Working Group, with the task of coordinating the implementation of the Action Plan. On 29 October 2024, the UB CoARA Working Group approved an updated version of the UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27, including revised lines of action, an updated timeline, and key actions. This second version of the [UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27](#) was published in the Zenodo repository, in line with the good practices [recommended by CoARA](#).

Annual monitoring of actions under the UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27

The main objective of this document is to report on monitoring of the implementation and degree of achievement of the actions set out in the UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27 that were scheduled to begin during 2024. In this first year of implementation, the actions taken address five of the six supporting commitments set out in the Agreement.

As a result of the monitoring exercise, some actions and their associated indicators have been reformulated. To ensure traceability, the changes made to these actions and indicators are detailed in the relevant table in section 3 of this document.

2. Monitoring of actions under the UB CoARA Action Plan: 2024

The table below summarizes the degree of achievement of the actions set out in the UB CoARA Action Plan that were scheduled to begin during 2024. The acronyms used in the lead responsible column refer to the original Catalan names of following academic positions:

DCOB: Delegate of the Rector for Scientific Journals and Open Science

VDOC: Vice-Rector for Doctoral Studies, Trainee Research Staff, Talent Attraction and Dissemination

VPDI: Vice-Rector assigned to the Rector and for Teaching and Research Staff

VPQU: Vice-Rector for Quality Policy

VREC: Vice-Rector for Research

CoARA commitments	Code for lines of action	Lines of action	Lead responsible	Code for actions	Actions	Start	End	Code for indicators	Assessment mechanisms (indicators)	2024 value	Started	Completed	Degree of achievement	Comments
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment.	CoARA05-01-000	Ensure institutional commitment to CoARA principles.	VPQU	CoARA05-001	Create the CoARA UB Working Group.	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	CoARA05-01-001-i1	Agreement to create the CoARA UB Working Group.	1		X	100%	Working group established.
			VPQU	CoARA05-01-002	Develop and approve the UB CoARA Action Plan.	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	CoARA05-01-002-i1	UB CoARA Action Plan document.	1		X	100%	Plan developed and approved. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1274471
			VPQU	CoARA05-01-003	Monitor the UB CoARA Action Plan annually.	Q3 2024	Q4 2027	CoARA05-01-003-i1	Annual monitoring report on the UB CoARA Action Plan.	1		X	100%	

CoARA commitments	Code for lines of action	Lines of action	Lead responsible	Code for actions	Actions	Start	End	Code for indicators	Assessment mechanisms (indicators)	2024 value	Started	Completed	Degree of achievement	Comments
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.	CoARA06-01-000	Align internal calls involving research assessment with the CoARA principles.	DCOB	CoARA06-01-001	Develop an institutional guide for research assessment based on the CoARA principles.	Q4 2024	Q4 2025	CoARA06-01-001-i1	Publication of the UB guide with recommendations for the assessment of research based on the CoARA principles.	0	X		25%	<p>A committee made up of the following members was established to develop the guide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Delegate of the Rector for Scientific Journals and Open Science · Delegate of the Rector for Internal Promotion of Research · An R4-level expert from the Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media · A member of the Institute of Complex Systems · A member of the UB's R2-level TRS · Senior officer for CoARA at the UB
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.	CoARA07-01-000	Train members of the UB community and publish and disseminate the CoARA principles.	VREC	CoARA07-01-003	Organize training activities on the CoARA principles for technical, management, and administrative and service staff involved in research management and assessment.	Q2 2024	Q4 2027	CoARA07-01-003-i1	% participation (of those invited).	0	X		25%	
								CoARA07-01-003-i2	Satisfaction of attendees with the training received.	0				Collection of information on the level of satisfaction has not yet begun.

CoARA commitments	Code for lines of action	Lines of action	Lead responsible	Code for actions	Actions	Start	End	Code for indicators	Assessment mechanisms (indicators)	2024 value	Started	Completed	Degree of achievement	Comments
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the CoARA coalition.	CoARA08-01-000	Promote the exchange of information and good practices with CoARA members.	VPQU	CoARA08-01-001	Promote the University of Barcelona's participation in the CoARA General Assembly, the Spanish National Chapter of CoARA, and, where strategically relevant, other specific working groups.	Q2 2024	Q4 2027	CoARA08-01-001-i1	Summary of participation in the annual monitoring report for the UB CoARA Action Plan.	1		X	100%	The UB participates in the CoARA working group Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts, within the Social Impact and Assessment section. The UB participates in Working Group 1 of the Spanish National Chapter of CoARA: Assessment Methodologies. Participation in the CoARA General Assembly (9 December 2024).
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the commitments; evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research; and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.	CoARA09-01-000	Promote an internal communication strategy on the implementation of the actions proposed in the UB CoARA Action Plan.	VPQU	CoARA09-01-001	Publish documentation, indicators and infographics on the UB CoARA website to report on progress in implementing the CoARA principles at the UB.	Q3 2024	Q4 2027	CoARA09-01-001-i1	Website updated	0	X		25%	The start date for implementing this action was brought forward to the last quarter of 2024. The website is expected to go live in the first quarter of 2025: ub.edu/coara .
				CoARA09-01-002	Implement and update internal and external communication channels on CoARA-related actions at the UB.	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	CoARA09-01-002-i1	Creation of a corporate email account	1		X	100%	Corporate email account activated: coara@ub.edu .

3. Summary of changes made to the actions set out in the UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27

This table summarizes the changes made to the actions set out in the UB CoARA Action Plan 2024–27 as a result of the monitoring exercise.

Action modified	Indicator modified	Modification
CoARA05-01-001. Create the CoARA UB Working Group.	—	Change of lead responsible
CoARA05-01-002. Develop and approve the UB CoARA Action Plan.	—	Change of lead responsible
CoARA09-01-001. Publish documentation, indicators and infographics on the UB CoARA website to report on progress in implementing the CoARA principles at the UB.	—	Implementation period changed.

4. Concluding remarks

The University of Barcelona has initiated the process of analyzing and implementing the principles for the reform of research assessment adopted by CoARA. An organizational and functional structure has been established, based on the University of Barcelona's CoARA Working Group. As a result of the Action Plan monitoring exercise, it was considered advisable to expand the working group through the incorporation of two experts in research evaluation and impact assessment, both with a solid track record in the field and internationally recognized standing. These new additions strengthen the UB CoARA Working Group and are expected to support the visibility and achievement of actions linked to Commitment 10 of the Agreement ("Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research").

A committee has been set up to develop an institutional guide to research assessment based on the CoARA principles, a core action of the Action Plan. The guide is intended to serve as the backbone for other actions to be carried out within the framework of the plan. The group tasked with developing the guide is coordinated by the delegate of the rector for Scientific Journals and Open Science.

The University of Barcelona is represented in the international forums of CoARA and actively participates in the working group Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research and Impacts. The UB also plays an active role in the [Spanish National Chapter of CoARA](#), taking part in its meetings and in one of the working groups established to analyze and implement the new research assessment principles (Working Group 1: Assessment Methodologies).

Monitoring has identified the need to improve dissemination of the actions being carried out under the CoARA framework across the University of Barcelona community. Dissemination efforts have begun with the activation of a corporate email account and the creation of a CoARA UB website, which is expected to be accessible by the end of the first quarter of 2025.

